

Simulation of Nonlinear H_∞ Observer for Sensorless Asynchronous Motor

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Abstract- This work concentrates on the synthesis of Induction Motor (IM) robust nonlinear H_∞ observer. The observer is synthesized to estimate non-measurable state variables, which are essential for control, and to ensure minimal disturbance effect on the system, despite parametric uncertainty presence and arbitrary noise. Linear Matrix Inequalities (LMI) are utilized to establish state observer stability criteria, where the observer gain matrices are calculated as a solution and maximum disturbance attenuation. Simulation results obtained demonstrate the suggested methodology effectiveness of sensorless considered IM control.

Keywords- Induction Motor, Nonlinear Observer, H_∞ observer, Lyapunov Stability, Linear Matrix Inequality (LMI).

I. INTRODUCTION

Induction motor drives are widely preferred in industry for their robustness, reliability, cost-effectiveness, low maintenance needs, and efficiency[1],[2]. The advancement of nonlinear control strategies and observers has further enhanced their popularity in industrial applications. However, induction motors are complex nonlinear systems, and their time-varying parameters present challenges for control, condition monitoring, and fault diagnostics. Additionally, state variables are not easily measurable and are influenced by variations in machine parameters, this poses additional problems for the control, diagnosis and monitoring of this machine [2].

Industrial processes typically need to understand unmeasurable state variables to achieve reliable sensorless control. The most cost-effective and efficient solution is to utilize state observers. An observer is a dynamic system that employs available input-output data to estimate these unmeasurable states. Acting as a “soft sensor,” it is vital not only for sensorless control techniques but also for condition monitoring, fault diagnosis, predictive maintenance, and fault-tolerant control strategies [1], [2][20-22].

In the past two decades, the design of nonlinear observers has garnered significant attention in the literature. Numerous efforts have been directed toward specific classes of nonlinear systems. These approaches can generally be categorized into several groups: nonlinear state linearization methods, high-gain observers, geometric algorithms, variable structure design procedures, and algebraic techniques[3], [4], [5], [6], [23].

Conversely, filtering to estimate unmeasurable state variables in systems with noisy measurements has been a significant challenge in signal processing and control. Generally, there are two main approaches to address this issue: the well-known Kalman filtering method and the H_∞ approach [10].

In the Kalman filtering approach, which has numerous practical applications, measurement noise is assumed to be Gaussian with known statistics. However, when the noise consists of arbitrary signals, the filtering problem can be addressed using the H_∞ observer [12][16].

This paper centers on the performance of the H_∞ observer design for induction motor (IM) systems. The H_∞ observer is employed to ensure robustness against nonlinearities, which are considered equivalent to various uncertainties arising from internal and external disturbances, as well as measurement noise[7], [8], [10], [11], [12], [13] [17].

A review of the literature reveals that various effective H_∞ filtering methods have been developed for different types of systems. Notable examples include H_∞ observers for one-sided Lipschitz nonlinear systems, H_∞ observers for singular Lipschitz nonlinear systems, and H_∞ control and filtering techniques for uncertain Markovian jump systems with time-varying delays [8], [9], [10], [11], [12][18].

To demonstrate the effectiveness of this H_∞ observer, we utilize a standard model of an induction motor. This nonlinear model is commonly employed for nonlinear control strategies, condition monitoring, and fault diagnosis in electric induction machine systems.

The paper is structured as follows: Sections two and three cover the theory of nonlinear observers and the implementation of the nonlinear observer, respectively. The robust H_∞ observer is discussed in section four. In the fifth section, we present the chosen nonlinear induction motor model. Finally, we provide simulation results along with commentary, concluding the paper with a summary of our findings.

II. H_∞ OBSERVER DESIGN, THE STOCHASTIC CASE

This section concentrates on the stochastic scenario of the robust H_∞ observer, which is used to systems that might include arbitrary signals and measurement uncertainties. [7][8][9][10][14].

By synthesizing a full-order filter, it is possible to validate a predetermined amount of disturbance reduction and asymptotically stable system.

We consider the stochastic system given as:

$$\dot{x} = Ax + R(x, u) + E_d w \quad (1)$$

$$y = Cx \quad (2)$$

w : Disturbance

$w \in l_2[0, \infty)$: An unknown exogenous disturbance

The H_∞ observer aims to reconstruct the state $x(t)$ of the disturbed system (1)-(2) while ensuring a certain precision.

We assume that $z = H\varepsilon(t)$,

H : A constant matrix that is known such that $\|z\| < \mu\|w\|$, with the constant $\mu > 0$.

The nonlinear observer corresponding to the system (1) - (2) is then illustrated by:

$$\dot{\hat{x}} = A\hat{x} + R(\hat{x}, u) + L[y - \hat{y}] \quad (3)$$

$$\hat{y} = C\hat{x} \quad (4)$$

Our goal is to determine the observer parameter L that simultaneously guarantees the following stated norm H_∞ upper bound and the asymptotic stability of the error dynamics.

Lemma 1: For any $x, y \in R^n$ and any positive definite matrix $P \in R^{n \times n}$, we have: $2x^T y \leq x^T P x + y^T P^{-1} y$

Using the abbaszadeh theorem 3 [16] for the system (1)-(2) with given Lipschitz constant γ and the corresponding observer (3)-(4), then, the errors dynamics of the observer is asymptotically stable, with the minimum of the norm l_2 and μ , if there exist scalars $\alpha_s > 1$, $\epsilon > 0$ and $\xi > 0$ and matrices $P > 0$ and R in order to offer a solution related to the ensuing LMI optimization challenge.

$$\begin{bmatrix} H^T H + \frac{1}{2}(\gamma + \frac{1}{\gamma} - 2\alpha_s) I & P E_d \\ E_d^T P & -\zeta I \end{bmatrix} < 0 \quad (5)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{1-\sigma^2(H)}{2\gamma} I & P \\ P & \frac{1-\sigma^2(H)}{2\gamma} I \end{bmatrix} < 0 \quad (6)$$

With: $L = P^{-1}R$ and $\mu^* \triangleq \min(\mu) = \sqrt{\zeta}$

Proof: We get the observer error dynamics as follows:

$$\dot{\varepsilon} = N\varepsilon + (R - R) + E_d w \quad (7)$$

Taking into account the Lyapunov function that listed below: $V = \varepsilon^T P \varepsilon$

Deriving this function, we get:

$$V = \varepsilon^T [N^T P + PN] \varepsilon + 2\varepsilon^T P (R - R) + \varepsilon^T P E_d w + w(t)^T E_d^T \varepsilon \quad (8)$$

Using **Lemma 1** leads to the following:

$$2\varepsilon^T P (R - R) \leq \varepsilon^T P \varepsilon + (R - R)^T P P^{-1} P (R - R) \quad (9)$$

$$2\varepsilon^T P (R - R) \leq \varepsilon^T P \varepsilon + (R - R)^T P (R - R) \quad (10)$$

To simplify relation (33), we can write that:

$$\varepsilon^T P \varepsilon \leq \lambda_{\max}(P) \|\varepsilon\|^2 = \lambda_{\max}(P) \varepsilon^T \varepsilon \quad (11)$$

$$\|(R - R)P(R - R)\|^T \leq \gamma^2 \lambda_{\max} \|\varepsilon\|^2 \quad (12)$$

In addition:

$$2\|\varepsilon^T P (R - R)\| \leq 2\gamma \lambda_{\max} \|\varepsilon\|_{\max}^2 \quad (13)$$

After replacing (35) - (36) in relation (33), we get: $2\gamma \lambda_{\max}(P) \|\varepsilon\|^2 \leq \lambda_{\max}(P) \|\varepsilon\|^2 + \gamma^2 \lambda_{\max}(P) \|\varepsilon\|^2$

Assume $Q = I$,

When we consider $w = 0$ in the deterministic situation, the time derivative of the Lyapunov function corresponding to this case takes the following form:

$$V(t) \leq -\varepsilon^T Q \varepsilon + 2\varepsilon^T (R - R) \leq 0 \quad (14)$$

$$V(t) \leq -\varepsilon^T I \varepsilon + 2\gamma \lambda_{\max} \|\varepsilon\|_{\max}^2 \quad (15)$$

Then:

$$1 - 2\gamma \lambda_{\max} \quad (16)$$

$$\sigma^-(P) \leq \frac{1}{2\gamma} \quad (17)$$

$$2\varepsilon^T P(R - R) \leq (1 + \gamma^2)\lambda T_{max} \quad (18)$$

$$2\varepsilon^T P(R - R) \leq (1 + \gamma^2) \frac{1}{2\gamma} (P)\varepsilon^T \varepsilon \leq \frac{1}{2}(\gamma + \frac{1}{\gamma})\varepsilon^T \varepsilon \quad (19)$$

In the general and stochastic case, we consider $w \neq 0$ and $Q = \alpha_s I$.

The time derivative of the Lyapunov function becomes:

$$V(t) = \varepsilon^T [N_1^T P + PN] \varepsilon + 2\varepsilon^T P(R - R) + \varepsilon^T P E_d w(t) + w(t)^T E^T P \varepsilon \quad (20)$$

$$V(t) \leq -\lambda T_{max} \frac{1}{2\gamma} \varepsilon^T \varepsilon + w^T(t) E^T P \varepsilon + \varepsilon^T P E_d w(t) \quad (21)$$

$$V(t) = -\alpha_s \varepsilon^T \varepsilon + \frac{1}{2}(\gamma + \frac{1}{\gamma}) \varepsilon^T \varepsilon + w^T(t) E_d P \varepsilon + \varepsilon^T P E_d w(t) \quad (22)$$

$$V(t) = [\frac{1}{2\gamma}(1 + \gamma^2) - \alpha] \varepsilon^T \varepsilon + w^T(t) E_d^T P \varepsilon + \varepsilon^T P E_d w(t) \quad (23)$$

$z = H\varepsilon(t)$, H is recognized as a constant with $\|z\| < \mu\|w\|$

Now, we define

$$J = \int_0^\infty (z^T z - \zeta w^T w) dt \quad (24)$$

By using the J criterion, the discrepancy between the energy caused by the disturbances and the estimation error energy can be minimized.

Thus:

$$J < \int_0^\infty (z^T z - \zeta w^T w) dt \quad (25)$$

So, a sufficient condition $J < 0$ is that:

$$\forall t \in [0, \infty), z^T z - \zeta w^T w + V(t) < 0$$

This means that: $z^T z - \zeta w^T w < 0$ (because $V(t)$ is a negative function), therefore:

$$\|z\|^2 < \zeta \|w\|^2 \Rightarrow \|z\| < \sqrt{\zeta} \|w\|.$$

Nevertheless, we have:

$$z^T z - \zeta w^T w + V(t) = \varepsilon^T H^T H \varepsilon - \zeta w^T w + V(t) \leq \varepsilon^T H^T H \varepsilon + [\frac{1}{2\gamma}(1 + \gamma^2) - \alpha] \varepsilon^T \varepsilon$$

$$+ \varepsilon^T P E_d w + w^T E^T P \varepsilon - \zeta w^T w \quad (26)$$

At that juncture, we can write:

$$J = [e^T \quad w^T] \begin{bmatrix} H^T H + [\frac{1}{2\gamma}(1 + \gamma^2) - \alpha] I & P E_d \\ E_d^T P & -\zeta I \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon \\ w \end{bmatrix} \quad (27)$$

Therefore, the following LMI having to be negative definite is a sufficient requirement for $J < 0$:

$$\begin{bmatrix} H^T H + [\frac{1}{2\gamma}(1 + \gamma^2) - \alpha] I & P E_d \\ E_d^T P & -\zeta I \end{bmatrix} < 0 \quad (28)$$

The relation equivalent to (28) can be rewritten using Schur's complement lemma:

$$H^T H + [\frac{1}{2\gamma}(1 + \gamma^2) - \alpha] I < \zeta I - \frac{1}{\zeta} P E_d E_d^T P < 0 \quad (29)$$

The third term is never negative; hence the equation's (30) negativity is dependent on how negatively the first and second terms add up:

$$H^T H + [2\gamma\lambda s_{max}] \quad (31)$$

As with every other symmetric matrix $H^T H$, though, we have

$$\lambda T_{max}^2 \sigma_{min}^2 \quad (32)$$

$$\sigma_{max}^2 \quad (33)$$

As stated by the definition of singular values

$$\bar{\sigma}^2(H) + 2\gamma\lambda s_{max} \quad (34)$$

Or:

$$\lambda \frac{\alpha_s - \bar{\sigma}^2(H)}{2\gamma} > \sigma_{max}^2 \quad (35)$$

This is equivalent to (6)

III. NON-LINEAR MODELING OF ASYNCHRONOUS MOTOR

In the reference frame of the stator fixed (α - β) axis, the nonlinear model of the IM introduced in this work is given as follows

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = f(x) + g(x).u \quad (36)$$

$$y = Cx \quad (37)$$

We note that the stator currents, rotor flux, and rotor speed are the state variables and the measurable vector components are the currents $i_{s\alpha}$ and $i_{s\beta}$. The controller vector $u = [u_{s\alpha}, u_{s\beta}, T_l]^T$.

Where:

$$f(x) = \begin{bmatrix} -\gamma i_{s\alpha} + \frac{\beta}{T_r} \varphi_{r\alpha} + \beta \omega \varphi_{r\beta} \\ -\gamma i_{s\beta} - \beta \omega \varphi_{r\beta} + \frac{\beta}{T_r} \varphi_{r\alpha} \\ m i_{s\alpha} - \frac{1}{T_r} \varphi_{r\alpha} - \omega \varphi_{r\beta} \\ m i_{s\beta} + \omega \varphi_{r\alpha} - \frac{1}{T_r} \varphi_{r\beta} \\ \partial (\varphi_{r\alpha} i_{s\beta} - \varphi_{r\beta} i_{s\alpha}) - k_f \omega - k T_l \end{bmatrix}, \quad g(x) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ \sigma L_s & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Where: $\gamma = \frac{1}{\sigma} \left(\frac{1}{T_s} + \frac{1-\sigma}{T_r} \right)$, $\sigma = 1 - \frac{m^2}{L_s L_r}$, $k_l = \frac{n_p}{J}$, $k_f = \frac{f_r}{J}$, $\partial = \frac{n^2 m}{J L_r}$, $\beta = \frac{1}{m} \left(\frac{1-\sigma}{\sigma} \right) = \frac{1}{\sigma} \frac{m}{L_s L_r}$ and, $\omega = n_p \Omega$.

The following notations are introduced in order to simplify the mathematical equation forms: $x_1 = i_{s\alpha}$, $x_2 = i_{s\beta}$, $x_3 = \varphi_{r\alpha}$, $x_4 = \varphi_{r\beta}$, $x_5 = \Omega$.

As we know IM model has a nonlinearity that results from multiplying the rotor flux components by the angular velocity in the first four equations, and multiplying the state variables in the system's dynamic equation. This model becomes more complex when We consider variability of IM parameters, such as rotor and/or stator resistances or inductances.

Fig. 1. Simulation scheme of H_∞ observer

IV. SIMULATION TESTS AND DISCUSSION

To demonstrate the reliability and the performance of the suggested nonlinear observer of the IM using a robust nonlinear H_∞ observer, we provide a series of simulations using MATLAB software.

The IM parameters are given in Table 1.

In simulation experiments of the robust observation scheme of IM, we must write the IM model in the form(1)-(2). For a good execution of the control scheme, we first start to solve the LMI conditions, relation (5) and relation (6), using a suitable LMI tool such as the LMI toolbox of MATLAB software.

To achieve robustness in the face of nonlinear uncertainty, we adopt Abbaszadeh's theorem 2 to maximize the appropriate Lipschitz constant γ , and then Abbaszadeh theorem 3 to minimize μ for the maximum γ .

$\epsilon = 0,04$, $\gamma^* = 0,7$, $\mu^* = 0,112$.

After that, employing Abbaszadeh theorem 3 [16], the LMI, (5), and (6) may be solved, and several simulation tests are carried out to determine the gains matrices L and R which guarantee the stability of the H_∞ observer.

In this diagram, we apply a disturbance to the supply voltage u of (IM), to see the impact of this disturbance on the performance of the system and in particular the performance of the observer.

$H = 10I$, $\alpha_s = 0.05$, $Q = 5I_5$, $E_d = 10V$

Table 1 Characteristics of the induction motor

Symbol	Quantity	Numerical value
P	Power	1.5 KW
f	Supply frequency	50 Hz
U	Supply voltage	220 V
n_p	Number of pair poles	2
R_s	Stator resistance	4.850 Ω
R_r	Rotor resistance	3.805 Ω
l_s	Stator inductance	0.274 H
l_r	Rotor inductance	0.274 H
m	Mutual inductance	0.258 H
ω_r	Rotor angular speed	297.25 rd/s
J	Inertia coefficient	0.03 kg/s
f_r	Fiction coefficient	0.00114 N.s/rd
T_l	Load torque	5 N.m

Note that the starting conditions $X_0 = [4 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0]$ for the initial state vector of the machine are taken into account in simulations of the observer. In simulation experiments of nonlinear H_∞ observers we must write the model of induction motor (36)-(37) in the form (5) - (6). As in the first observer approach, the simulation of the nonlinear H_∞ approach is performed in two steps, the first simulation step consists of resolving the LMI conditions, relation (5)-(6), using an adequate LMI tool such as the LMI tool-box of the Matlab software. To ensure robustness against nonlinear uncertainty, we use theorem 1 to maximize the admissible Lipschitz constant γ and then theorem 2, to minimize μ for the maximized γ .

$$\gamma^* = 0,7, \mu^* = 0,112, \varepsilon = 0,04.$$

Subsequently, from Theorem 2 and solving the LMI, (5), (6), then we calculate the nonlinear observer gain matrices L and G .

In this observer, we apply a disturbance in the power supply u to see these performances.

$$H = 10I, \alpha_s = 0.05, Q = 5I_5, B_d = 20$$

$$P = \begin{bmatrix} 0.0005 & 0 & 0.0143 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.0005 & 0 & 0.0143 & 0 \\ 0.0143 & 0 & 0.4552 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.0143 & 0 & 0.4552 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1.6924 \end{bmatrix} \quad G = \begin{bmatrix} -0.0574 & 0 \\ 0 & -0.0574 \\ -1.7151 & 0 \\ 0 & -1.7151 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$L = \begin{bmatrix} -213.5922 & 0 \\ 0 & -213.5922 \\ 2.9415 & 0 \\ 0 & 2.9415 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Using an S-function-based Matlab application that interfaces with the Matlab Simulink software, the computed numerical values of the gain matrix and the vectors are injected into the simulation in the second stage, which simulates the nonlinear system and the nonlinear H_∞ observer.

The simulation findings of the designed and nonlinear H_∞ observer are displayed in the following. Fig.3 and fig.4 present the measured and estimated stator current and rotor flux components respectively. Fig.5 and Fig.6 illustrate the measured and estimated rotor speed and the corresponding load torque respectively with corresponding estimation error. One can see that the observed state variables of the machine follow the intended trajectories.

Fig. 2. Perturbation of stator voltage

Fig. 3. Real, Observed ($I_{s\alpha}$), Estimation Error

According to fig.5, we note a good trajectory tracking of the speed in the presence of disturbances and show the high performance of the observer H_∞ .

The simulation results demonstrate that, despite the partly unknown transition probabilities, the designed H_∞ filters are feasible and effective, ensuring the error systems are stochastically stable.

Fig. 4. Real, Observed, and Estimation Error ($\varphi_{r\alpha}$)

Fig. 5. Real, Observed, and Estimation Error (ω_r)

Fig. 6. Real and Observed Electromechanical Torque

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have addressed the nonlinear H_∞ observer design for the sensorless induction motor drive.

The performance of the nonlinear observers is evaluated in terms of their ability to cope with model imperfections and process uncertainties such as measurement errors and uncertain initial conditions.

Based on the simulation results, the proposed observer proved to be robust when IM load changes occur in the presence of disturbances. On the other hand, the results obtained using the nonlinear H_∞ observer show that three characteristics can be obtained simultaneously. Asymptotic stability, robustness against nonlinear uncertainty, and minimized guaranteed H_∞ cost.

VI. REFERENCES

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